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Synthesis and characterization of La₂Ce₂O₇ powder and mechanical properties of La₂Ce₂O₇/YSZ composites

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Abstract:

Lanthanum cerium oxide, La₂Ce₂O₇ (LC), has attracted increasing interest as a promising material for TBCs because of its high phase stability and potential capability to be operated above 1250 °C. Moreover, LC exhibits lower thermal conductivity and higher coefficient of thermal expansion than the conventional yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) material [1]. However, TBCs based on LC/YSZ showed a better thermal cycling behavior than single LC or YSZ coating [2]. Therefore, a coating structure and its composition should be rationally designed to utilize the advantages of LC. In this work, LC powder was synthesized by solid-state reaction and investigated as a material for TBC application. Moreover, LC/YSZ composites with different weight fractions of YSZ (40 – 70 wt. %) were prepared by conventional mixing of LC and YSZ powders, followed by sintering of the powders via hot pressing at 1400 °C for 1 h. The effect of YSZ addition on the microstructure and mechanical properties, i. e. Vickers hardness and indentation fracture resistance, was investigated.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the prepared LC powder revealed agglomerated structure consisting of finely and uniformly distributed grains with size up to 10 μm. The fluorite structure of the LC powder after annealing at 1400 °C was confirmed by X-Ray diffraction (XRD). The thermal behavior of the LC powder was analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in the temperature range of 25 °C-1350 °C. Result shows high phase stability of the LC powder and its suitability for TBC applications. The hardness value of LC/YSZ composites increased with increasing mass fraction of YSZ particles. The LC/70YSZ composite material reached the highest hardness (12 GPa), while the hardness of LC/40YSZ was only 10 GPa.

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